

Religion of Roman Palmyra

By Aleksandra KubiakSchneider, University of Wrocław

Entry tags: Roman Religions, Temenos, Levantine Religion, Greek Cult, Graeco-Roman, shrines, City, Religious Practice, Archaeological monument, Shrine, Phoenician Cult, Palmyra, Arabian Religions, Aramaic Religions, Hellenistic Religions, Greek Religions, Mesopotamian Religions, Monument, Temple, Altar, Religious Place, Religious Group, Religious Complex

Tadmor-Palmyra, an ancient city located in an oasis in the middle of Syrian dry steppe (commonly known as Syrian Desert), has a long occupation history from the Bronze Age to modern times. Double naming shows the city's multicultural background. Tadmor is the original Aramaic name of the place, while Palmyra was used by Greeks and Romans. These two names are not exactly a translation. Pliny the Elder in his *Historia Naturalis* described Palmyra, that it was situated between two empires: Roman and Parthian and grew up on the rich soil. Being between two empires required great diplomatic skills, which the Palmyrenes mastered in their long distance trade, sending caravans to Spasinou-Charax, ships to India and Arabia, etc. The trade and particular situation of Palmyra on the geopolitical arena, being long independent, resulted in urban development and the appearance of monumental architecture: columned streets, theater, monumental tombs (tower-tombs, hypogeous and funerary temples) and temples. Palmyra also had an advanced epigraphic culture. The city provides about 3000 inscriptions of different sorts: honorific, funerary, religious, etc. written mostly in the local dialect of Aramaic, but also many texts in Greek and only a few in Latin. The city provides an important material culture: epigraphical, iconographical and archaeological remains concerning the gods and their worship. About 40 divine names and titles are known through the written sources from Palmyra. Palmyrenes show themselves in the sources as multicultural society worshipping the deities of various origins: Mesopotamian, Phoenician, Aramaic, and Arabic. The divine protector of Palmyra was Bel, the Lord of Universe and Fate (of Mesopotamian origins), having the largest temple in the city, the ruins of which were destroyed in 2015 by terrorists. It hosted not only a temple devoted to Palmyrene gods, as it was labelled in the inscriptions, but later also a church and a mosque. The temenos was until 1930' literally a house of Tadmoreans, where a modern village was located. Second in size, was the temple of Ba'alshamin, the storm god. Beside these two, there were also temples of the goddess Allat, of the god Nabu (or Nebo), of Arsu, of Belhammon and Manawat, of Rabbaseire, of Yarhibol, of Aglibol and Malakbel (so-called Sacred Garden) and of Atargatis. However, the latter was never discovered and is only attested in the inscriptions. In the Late Antiquity, Palmyra was a bishop's seat and had at least 6 churches.

Date Range: 44 BCE - 272 CE

Region: Palmyra

Region tags: Middle East, Syria

Palmyra, Syria

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Ted Kaizer, *Religious Life of Palmyra*, Stuttgart: Steiner Verlag, 2002
- Source 2: Aleksandra Kubiak-Scheider, *Des dédicaces sans théonyme de Palmyre. Béni (soit) son nom pour l'éternité.*, RGRW 197; Brill: Leiden, 2021
- Source 3: Michał Gawlikowski, *Des dieux de Palmyre, Aufstieg und Niedergang der römischen Welt* II.18.4, 1990, pp. 2605-2658

Reference: Dirven, Lucinda. *The Palmyrenes of Dura-europos*. BRILL, 1999.
https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Palmyrenes_of_Dura_Europos.html?hl=&id=SeI5DwAAQBAJ.

Reference: Kaizer, Ted. *Religious Life of Palmyra*. Stuttgart: Steiner Verlag, 2002.

Reference: Kubiak-Schneider, Aleksandra. *Des Dédicaces Sans Théonyme De Palmyre. Béni (soit) Son Nom Pour L'éternité.* Vol. 197. Leiden-Boston: Brill, 2021.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://base-map-polytheisms.huma-num.fr>
- Source 1 Description: Database of the Mapping Ancient Polytheisms Project on the divine names
- Source 2 URL: <https://virtual-museum-syria.org>
- Source 2 Description: Collection of the monuments from the Museum of Palmyra

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Palmyra was excavated by international archaeological missions. The countries, which had a regular, scientific digs in different sectors of the ancient city until 2011, were among others: Poland (Kazimierz Michałowski, Michał Gawlikowski, Grzegorz Majcherek), Austria-Germany (Andreas Schmidt-Colinet), Japan (Kiyohide Saito), USA (Cynthia Finlayson), France (Cmte du Mesnil du Buisson, Christiane Delplace), Syria (Khalil al-Hariri)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1930-2011

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

– Year range: 1959-2011

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Polish Archaeological Mission

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Type of excavation:

– Illicit

Notes: Since 2011 Palmyra is an arena of illicit excavations and destruction of the monuments.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 2011-ongoing

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Water source

– Other [specify]: dry steppe / desert

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ A single structure

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: mountains, oasis

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: communal and individual

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

–Other [specify]: exploded

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–For religious reasons

- For political reasons
- As the result of war
- As the result of pillage

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
– Natural phenomena

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Syria

↳ In antiquity
– More than once

Specific to this answer:
Region: Syria

↳ In modernity
– Post-Renaissance

Specific to this answer:
Region: Syria

– No

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Syria

↳ A single structure
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Syria

↳ A group of structures:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Palmyra was a house of many temples dedicated to the gods. To the most important belong the temple of Bel, temple of Baalshamin, temple of Nabu, temple of Allat. There were also small shrines located along the wadi (e.g. of Arsu or Rabbaseire). There was also a sanctuary located on top of the Jebel Muntar in the Southern part of the city.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: goddess Allat

– Yes [specify]: god Bel and other gods

– Yes [specify]: Baalshamin - the lord go heavens

– Yes [specify]: Nabu

– Yes [specify]: Yarhibol

– Yes [specify]: Belhammon and Manawat

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: It was dedicated to more than one god. There are many temples in Palmyra dedicated to different deities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

–Other [specify]: Families and tribes

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Specify

– Religious specialists affiliated with political entity

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Specify

– Private individual

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Groups:

– Priests

– Men

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

– Women

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Specify

– Other [specify]: New Year festival and the arrival of the statue of the god

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expectation of favor in return

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

– Thanksgiving to a god/gods for favor received

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

– Other [specify]: organizing festivals dedicated to the gods

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible that the sanctuary held a library of texts (like the epos of creation and astronomical observations), however nothing is preserved nowadays.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 400

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 15

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Earth

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– I don't know

↳ Plaster

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Maybe there were wooden parts in the temple, but not preserved today.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: it is local limestone, most probably there were also other stones used (e.g. marble)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: metal

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: architectural features: columns, merlons, pilars

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

Notes: there was a decoration inside of the temples and outside, so it was both: hidden from the public view as well as seen by a mass.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Notes: there were in the antiquity, nowadays not present

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There must have been statues in the temples, because the special installations are attested archaeologically (see temple of Allat, Gawlikowski 2017).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: The temples like temple of Bel, Allat and Baalshamin were places of setting the honorific statues for the people who contributed to the temple community and to the city.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Notes: in the temple of Bel there is preserved mythological scene showing a combat of deities against sea monster Tiamat.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Some reliefs show the ritual procedures, like burning incense, processions and greeting the deities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Zodiac, floral motives, cultic furniture

Notes: The texts mention the dedication to the gods the furnitures like cultic beds and mattresses.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: They exist only in the funerary context, representing the curtains and banquets.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Humans

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: sculptures

↳ Other

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: sarcophagi

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: there are also goddesses and minor deities

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ In dreams:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In trance possession:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is the cult statue visible:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Libations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Offerings of food:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ **Animal sacrifice:**
– Yes [specify]: not bloody at the temple of Allat
Specific to this answer:
Region: Syria

↳ **Human sacrifice:**
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Syria

↳ **Sacred objects:**
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Syria

↳ **Daily life objects:**
– Field doesn't know
Specific to this answer:
Region: Syria

↳ **Supernatural beings care about sex:**
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Syria

↳ **Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:**
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Syria

↳ **Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:**
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Syria

↳ **Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: unspecified animals

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

– Yes

Notes: there are also incense burning offerings, libations and banquets

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Priests

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Local elites

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Private contributions

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: other temple members: barbers, butchers, bakers, etc.

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: banquet halls

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Notes: The major festival was the New Year celebration practiced in the month Nisan. The second celebration was the festival of premises in the month of Tishri. See Kubiak-Schneider 2021, 43.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: at least 2 times per year

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– Elites

– Non-elites

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The festivals, especially the taking a share from the cultic meals were most probably reserved for the ritual professionals. See Kubiak-Schneider 2022.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: we do not know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Elites

– Religious professionals

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

– Yes

↳ Species

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Part
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Remains are consumed:
 - Yes
- ↳ Remains are disposed of:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Divination through human communication:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is a human being the vehicle for the oracle:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is a human being the interpreter of the oracle:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified sex/gender:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified ethnicity:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified class:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is sex-deprivation required:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Are intoxicants required:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Physical ordeal required:
 - Yes

- ↳ Divination through animal-behavior:
 - Field doesn't know

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

- ↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
 - Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

- ↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
 - Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

- ↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
 - specify: we do not know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

- ↳ How often do these rituals take place:
 - specify: every day

- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: We know about priests (kmry), apkalli-sages ('pkl), but also different associations mentioned in the Palmyrene tesserae.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Present full time

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Present part time

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Function for water management:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: election of the clergy

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We can assume that yes, but nothing is preserved nowadays.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: There are votive dedications placed on the stone altars, written in Palmyrene Aramaic.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

↳ Are they oral:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Most probably some traditions were oral, like reciting hymns. The recitation of religious poems is marked by the use of the formulae "Blessed be his name forever", "They called upon the god in the hour of trouble and he made a miracle in the day of justice" (PAT 1928). The

language of many votive dedications reveal the existence of the religious poetry.

Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– No

Notes: However there is an inscription from 32 CE speaking about consecration of the temple of Bel (PAT 1347). Furthermore, one of the reliefs from the temple of Bel represents the procession interpreted by scholars (e.g. L. Driven, M. Gawlikowski) as foundation of major cults of Bel and Allat.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Palmyrene tesserae (see H. Ingholt, H. Seyrig, J. Starcky, A. Caquot, *Recueil des Tesselles de Palmyre*, Paris, 1955; Raja 2020; Kubiak-Schneider 2022) attest the function of diviners and exorcists who must have served with the incantations. Furthermore, there are apkalli, the sages, who must have been the "theologians" of the cultic practices.

Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Syria

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Religion of Roman Palmyra, Kaizer, Ted. *Religious Life of Palmyra*. Stuttgart: Steiner Verlag, 2002.

Reference: Religion of Roman Palmyra, Raja, Rubina. *Pearl of the Desert: A History of Palmyra*. Oxford University Press, 2022.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Pearl_of_the_Desert_a_History_of_Palmyra.html?hl=&id=KZBOEAAAQBAJ.

Reference: Religion of Roman Palmyra, Andrade, Nathanael. *Zenobia*. Oxford University Press, 2018. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=erhwDwAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Religion of Roman Palmyra, Aruz, Joan, Waleed Khaled al-Asa'ad, Eleonora Cussini, Lucinda Dirven, Michał Gawlikowski, Maura K. Heyn, Ted Kaizer, et al.. *Palmyra*. Metropolitan Museum of Art, 2018. <https://books.google.com/books/about/Palmyra.html?hl=&id=5D5nDwAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Religion of Roman Palmyra, Hillers, Delbert R., and Eleonora Cussini. *A Journey to Palmyra*. BRILL, 2005. https://books.google.com/books/about/A_Journey_to_Palmyra.html?hl=&id=oZcr7SzzVYYC.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Source 1: Ted Kaizer, *Religious Life of Palmyra*, Stuttgart: Steiner Verlag, 2002, Source 2: Aleksandra Kubiak-Scheider, *Des dédicaces sans théonyme de Palmyre. Béni (soit) son nom pour l'éternité.*, RGRW 197; Brill: Leiden, 2021, Source 3: Michał Gawlikowski, *Des dieux de Palmyre, Aufstieg und Niedergang der römischen Welt II.18,4*, 1990, pp. 2605-2658, Dirven, Lucinda. *The Palmyrenes of Dura-europos*. BRILL, 1999. https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Palmyrenes_of_Dura_Europos.html?hl=&id=Sel5DwAAQBAJ.

Reference: Source 1: Ted Kaizer, *Religious Life of Palmyra*, Stuttgart: Steiner Verlag, 2002, Source 2: Aleksandra Kubiak-Scheider, *Des dédicaces sans théonyme de Palmyre. Béni (soit) son nom pour l'éternité.*, RGRW 197; Brill: Leiden, 2021, Source 3: Michał Gawlikowski, *Des dieux de Palmyre, Aufstieg und Niedergang der römischen Welt II.18,4*, 1990, pp. 2605-2658, Kaizer, Ted. *Religious Life of Palmyra*. Stuttgart: Steiner Verlag, 2002.

Reference: Source 1: Ted Kaizer, *Religious Life of Palmyra*, Stuttgart: Steiner Verlag, 2002, Source 2: Aleksandra Kubiak-Scheider, *Des dédicaces sans théonyme de Palmyre. Béni (soit) son nom pour l'éternité.*, RGRW 197; Brill: Leiden, 2021, Source 3: Michał Gawlikowski, *Des dieux de Palmyre, Aufstieg und Niedergang der römischen Welt II.18,4*, 1990, pp. 2605-2658, Kubiak-Schneider, Aleksandra. *Des Dédicaces Sans Théonyme De Palmyre. Béni (soit) Son Nom Pour L'éternité.*. Vol. 197. Leiden-Boston: Brill, 2021.